

IMPROPER DIET CAUSES DISEASE.

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Eating is the basic biological need of life. Food, in turn, provides the energy necessary for the development and regulation of metabolism of the organism, ensures the growth and proper formation of the organism, and health maintenance. Food products should be useful, diverse, nutritious and quantitatively optimal.

Skipping breakfast, frequent snacking, eating a lot of sweets, eating salty foods - all these are the most harmful eating habits. Persistent violations of healthy eating habits lead to an increase in overweight and chronic diseases among adolescents. Currently, the increase in the number of diseases such as obesity and related diseases such as diabetes and cardiovascular diseases among teenagers is a serious concern.

Malnutrition causes the growing organism to be unable to saturate itself with necessary nutrients. For example, a diet low in iron causes iron deficiency anemia to occur more frequently. Observations conducted in the world's leading scientific centers confirm that excessive consumption of foods and sweets made from animal fat and high-quality flour products, failure to follow the order and rhythm of eating, leads to a violation of the balance between the main components of food and, as a result, to the occurrence of these diseases. Because they are one of the main causes of increased cholesterol (fatty particles) in the blood, high blood pressure, myocardial infarction, cerebral hemorrhage or ischemic stroke (acute blood circulation disorder due to accumulation of fat in the brain and neck vessels), diabetes mellitus. . Currently, the number of overweight, that is, obese people is increasing all over the world. Doctors of the world are worried that by 2025, the number of people suffering from obesity may double if appropriate measures are not taken. NIGOH Regular exercise reduces systolic (upper) and diastolic (lower) blood pressure by 5-10 mm. lowers the mercury column, has a positive effect on fat metabolism in the blood and reduces the amount of cholesterol that causes heart diseases. The signing of the decree of the head of our country "On measures for the wide implementation of a healthy lifestyle and further development of mass sports" provides for the prevention of these diseases. As noted in the decree, the occurrence of the

COVID-19 pandemic has shown that the health, physical health, and healthy lifestyle of the population are weak in Uzbekistan as well as in other countries of the world. The new type of coronavirus is mainly life-threatening for patients with cardiovascular and respiratory diseases and co-morbidities such as obesity (overweight). The concept of a healthy lifestyle has a broad meaning, it includes physical activity, harmful habits, such as drug addiction, tobacco smoking, alcohol consumption, and rational nutrition. At this point, it should be remembered that among the thousands of factors that affect the human body, nutrition, especially eating at the right time and in moderation, and when necessary, consuming dietary food, is of leading importance. From a medical point of view, eating is recommended in different order and composition to prevent the disease, depending on the age, body structure, climate, disease, its type and period. Only then can a person live a long, healthy and prosperous life. From a medical point of view, it is advisable to eat four times a day and at the same time every day. About 25% of it corresponds to the first breakfast, 15% to the second breakfast, 35% to the lunch, and 25% to the dinner, which is the main condition for a healthy diet. It is very important to pay attention to its composition when eating. Since protein-rich foods increase the excitability of the nervous system, it is better to eat them in the first half of the day, when a person is actively moving. Otherwise, it prevents sleep or deep sleep from occurring. When dinner is the majority of the daily diet, the oxidation of fats is not fully observed, which leads to a tendency to obesity. Organizing a healthy diet provides an opportunity for good digestion of nutrients. An increase in the amount and number of meals reduces the excitability of the digestive center and suppresses appetite. Food consumed by people over the age of 50 should not exceed 2500-2600 calories and the amount of fat and sugar should be strictly limited. We would like to emphasize that dinner should be eaten at least 2-3 hours before bedtime. Meat and fish dishes (including fatty ones) should be eaten mainly in the morning and afternoon. It is advisable to have a sharp limitation of table salt in the dinner, and to have more milk dishes. Because they do not change the physiological activity of the body during sleep. Unlike them, salty and meaty foods have a negative effect on the cardiovascular and respiratory systems, causing an increase in blood pressure, heart rate and breathing rate, rather than a decrease. It should not be forgotten that the foods consumed are rich in fiber (black, dried and baked bread, etc.), vitamins, potassium and magnesium salts, and the preparation of food in vegetable oil prevents the development of sclerosis in blood vessels. In the daily menu, salads

made from vegetables and fruits, vinaigrettes, cabbage, tomatoes, cucumbers, zucchini, cilantro should be in sufficient quantity, and legumes, that is, peas, beans, mash, as well as various mushrooms should be used in limited quantities. Cheese and cottage cheese made from skimmed milk are also useful. Non-bitter tea, fruit juices, herbal infusions are recommended for drinking. In a word, the diversity of the food diet and their positive effect on the human body can stop or slow down the processes that lead to aging and disease. Regularly living a physically active life moderates cardiovascular activity and prevents disease. Regular exercise reduces systolic (upper) and diastolic (lower) blood pressure by 5-10 mm. lowers the mercury column, has a positive effect on fat metabolism in the blood and reduces the amount of cholesterol that causes heart diseases. It also regulates the body's demand for energy and its consumption, improves mood and general condition. Increased resistance to carbohydrates (diabetes), reducing the risk of obesity, musculoskeletal diseases and tumors is directly related to regular physical activity. Movement shapes our bodies. Physical education embodies discipline, will, organization, hard work, high intellectual faith and valuable qualities of social importance. It illuminates the biological capabilities of the organism. At this point, it is worth saying that conditioning the body (water treatments) increases its resistance to adverse climatic conditions, i.e. heat or cold. Also, getting used to going to bed and waking up at the right time every day, taking a light shower is effective for human health. Getting at least seven hours of sleep every day will boost your tomorrow's performance.

CONCLUSION When organizing a proper diet, first of all, the use of many plant products will have a positive effect on the digestion of the necessary plant fiber. The fibers in it are not digested in the stomach, enter the large intestine and become food for beneficial bacteria. Fiber helps improve metabolism and prevent constipation. In addition, dairy products have a positive effect on the gastrointestinal tract. If you do not have a lactose deficiency, these products should also be included in the diet. There is a vital and natural connection between human psyche and health. A healthy body, a healthy mind, a healthy perception, a healthy spirit must be common to every person. Stress and negative factors are the cause of all diseases. Take care of yourself from nervousness and mental stress.

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